

Speculation on Entropy Increase for Two Combined Tsallis Systems

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Jan. 31, 2025

It is well-known that allowing two systems at different temperatures which obey Shannon's entropy to equilibrate with no work done leads to an increase in entropy (which follows the second law of thermodynamics). In (1), a proof is presented showing that an increase in entropy also applies to two systems described by Tsallis entropy. Here, we present an alternative argument based on the known fact that for $q=1$ the change in entropy is greater than 0. Even though d and $d1d2$ change with q , the Tsallis entropy: $1/(1-q) \int d \text{ phase } (d \text{ power } q - (d1d2) \text{ power } q)$ must be positive for $q=1+\delta$ (where δ is positive and tiny). This suggests that $q=1$ introduces a bias in $d1d2$ leading to it having more large values than d , we argue, and hence forcing the integral $\int d \text{ phase } (d \text{ power } q - (d1d2) \text{ power } q)$ to be negative. We suggest that once this bias is introduced for $q>1$, there is no reason for it to change. In particular, for $\Delta S = 0$ (which would be needed before one could have $\Delta S < 0$), one would require $d=d1d2$ meaning that the equilibration process did nothing, i.e. did not change d from $d1d2$, we argue.

Shannon Case

It is well known that allowing two ideal gases (described by Shannon's entropy) to equilibrate through thermal means (one box next to the other) leads to an increase in entropy. It is also known that Shannon's entropy - $\sum_i p(i) \ln(p(i))$ is additive for $p = p1*p2$. For instance, $E=3/2 N RT$, so if the two gases are identical (same volume and N) except for temperature, that by information arguments, the final equilibrated temperature of both should be the same and there should be no change in energy. Thus:

$$3/2 N R T_1 + 3/2 N R T_2 = 3/2 N R 2T \rightarrow T = (T_1+T_2)/2 \quad ((1))$$

Using the first law of thermodynamics: $dE = TdS \rightarrow C dT/T = dS$ one may compute the change in entropy: ($C = 3/2N$)

$$\text{Change in entropy } S = S((T_1+T_2)/2, 2N) - S(N, T_1) - S(N, T_2) =$$

$$\int_{T_1}^{(T_1+T_2)/2} C dT/T + \int_{T_2}^{(T_1+T_2)/2} C dT/T$$

$$= 2C \ln(.5 (T_1+T_2)/\sqrt{T_1 T_2}) \quad ((2)) \text{ with } C>0 \text{ and } T_1+T_2 > \sqrt{2} \sqrt{T_1 T_2}$$

$$= 2C \ln(.7 B) > 0 \text{ because } B>1 \quad ((2))$$

Alternatively, using the Sackur-Tetrode equation (1),

$$S = N \ln \{ V/N (CT/N)^{3/2} \} + N 5/2 \quad ((3)) \quad (C=3/2N)$$

one has:

$$2N \ln \left\{ 2 \frac{(T_1+T_2)}{\sqrt{T_1 T_2}} \right\} + 2N \ln(2) > 0 \text{ because } T_1+T_2 > \sqrt{T_1 T_2} \quad ((4))$$

Tsallis Case According to (1)

We first present the argument for: change in $S > 0$ given in (1). The quantity of interest is:

$$\text{Change in } S = \frac{1}{(1-q)} \int (d^{\text{power } q} - (d_1 d_2)^{\text{power } q}) d\text{phasespace} \quad ((5))$$

Here d_1 and d_2 are the probability densities of the two systems and d of the equilibrated one. The goal is to show ((5)) is greater than 0.

In (1), X is defined as: $\left\{ 1 - (d_1 d_2 / d)^{\text{power } q} \right\} / (1-q)$ ((6a)) and

$$C_q = \int d^{\text{power } q} d\text{phase} \quad ((6b))$$

Then: change in $S = c_q \langle X_q \rangle$ where $\langle X_q \rangle = \int d^{\text{power } q} X_q d\text{phase} / c_q$ ((7a)) or

$$\text{Change in } S = \frac{1}{(1-q)} \int (d^{\text{power } q} - (d_1 d_2)^{\text{power } q}) d\text{phase} \quad ((7b))$$

((7)) is shown to be:

$$\text{Change in } S = \int d X_q d\text{phase} + \frac{1}{(T c_q)} \int (d^{\text{power } q} - (d_1 d_2)^{\text{power } q}) (H - U_q) d\text{phase} \quad ((8))$$

Where H is the Hamiltonian and U_q is related to the potential (see (1)). The argument of (1) is that the $H - U_q$ integral is zero and the first term on the RHS of ((8)) is positive if one uses the relation:

$$\left\{ 1 - (d_1 d_2 / d)^{\text{power } q} \right\} > q \left\{ 1 - d_1 d_2 / d \right\}. \quad ((9))$$

We try to show that: change in S for the Tsallis case is greater than 0 using a different method.

Different Method for Showing that the Change in S Tsallis > 0 for Two Systems

We begin with the result that for $q=1$, the Tsallis scenario yields the Shannon one. It is already known that in the Shannon's scenario, change in $S > 0$. (Furthermore, (1) proves this as well.) This means that:

$$M = \frac{1}{(1-q)} \int (d^{\text{power } q} - (d_1 d_2)^{\text{power } q}) d\text{phase} \quad ((10))$$

must be positive for all q for the second law of thermodynamics to hold. For $q=1$, $1-q=0$ so the integral in ((10)) must also be 0. This means that:

$$\int (d - d_1 d_2) d\text{phase} = 0 \quad ((11))$$

If one considers $q = 1 + \delta$, where δ is tiny, then $1/1-q$ is negative and the integral in ((10)) must also be negative because even though d , d_1 and d_2 are functions of q , one cannot have an immediate jump in a function ((10)) from a positive value for $q=1$ to a negative value (or even 0 value) for $q=1+\delta$. We assume that M is not infinitesimal for $q=1$.

$$\text{Now: } \int d \text{ dphase} = 1 = \int d_1 d_2 \text{ dphase} \text{ by normalization } ((12))$$

As a result, a bias is introduced when $q \rightarrow 1 + \delta$ because the integral in ((10)) is negative, meaning that $\int d \text{ power } q \text{ dphase} < \int (d_1 d_2) \text{ power } q \text{ dphase}$. If $d=d_1 d_2$, then the two integrals would be the same. Thus, d and $d_1 d_2$ cannot be the same. One may now write the integrals as a sum. The normalization condition ((12)) suggests that one may group two values of d (from an ordered vector of d values) with one value of $d_1 d_2$, e.g.

$$\frac{2}{3} dx = \frac{1}{3} dx + \frac{1}{3} dx \quad ((13))$$

Such a scheme shows that both integrals in ((12)) may be satisfied, but any power >1 shows that in ((13)) one side is greater than the other, e.g. for $q=2$

$$\frac{4}{9} > \frac{1}{9} + \frac{1}{9} \quad ((14))$$

In other words we argue that if ((12)) holds for any $q>1$, then one cannot have

$$\int d\text{phase } d \text{ power } q - (d_1 d_2) \text{ power } q = 0 \quad ((15)).$$

Note: One could have a d and $d_1 d_2$ which are mirror images of each other. This means, however, that d and $d_1 d_2$ essentially have the same values just at different x positions, i.e. the same ordered vectors. In such a case, not only does ((12)) hold, but the integral of ((10)) is 0 for all q values. Thus, an ordered vector set: $(d(x_a), d(x_b) \dots)$ such that $d(x_a) > d(x_b) > d(x_c)$ etc must differ from the same ordered vector for $d_1 d_2$. If there is a bias in one set, such that fewer $d(x_i)$ values are larger than $d_1(x_j) d_2(x_j)$ values, then for ((12)) to hold, one have a more $d_1(x_a) d_2(x_a) = d(x_i) + d(x_j)$, which means that taking any q power gives a bias to $d_1 d_2$, i.e. its integral is larger than that of $d \text{ power } q$ even though ((12)) holds. With a bias present, one can never have the integral in ((10)) equal 0 for $q>1$.

This implies that for $q=1$, one has a positive entropy change which can never change to zero for a $q>1$. If this is the case, then the change in entropy cannot become negative, because it would first have to become 0 for some q .

In other words, we argue that $q=1$ introduces a bias into ((10)) which means that the integral favors d_1d_2 over d for $q=1+\delta$ and it seems that this trend cannot be reversed. For $q=0$, $\Delta S = 0$ and this should increase to the positive value at $q=1$, so change in S is positive for $q=0$ to $q=1$.

In particular, for $\Delta S = 0$, one would require that $d=d_1d_2$ which means that the equilibrium did nothing.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that given $\int d \, d\text{phase} = 1$ and $\int d_1d_2 \, d\text{phase}$, where d represent two equilibrated Tsallis systems and d_1 and d_2 the initial unequilibrated Tsallis systems, and change in entropy: $1/(1-q) \int d \, d\text{phase} (d^q - (d_1d_2)^q)$, a bias is introduced with $q=1$. For $q=1$, one has change in entropy >0 meaning that it should also be >0 for $q=1+\delta$, where $\delta > 0$ and tiny. Thus, the integral of $(d_1d_2)^q$ is greater than that of d^q meaning that ordered vectors of values of d_1d_2 and d cannot be the same. In fact, due to the bias, one expects the d_1d_2 ordered vector to contain more large numbers than the d one so that a power of q distinguishes between the two. We argue that the bias introduced with $q=1$ does not get changed with changing q as one may show a reason for the bias appearing in the first place, but no reason for $\int d \, d\text{phase} = \int d_1d_2 \, d\text{phase} = 1$ and $\int d \, d\text{phase} d^q = \int d_1d_2 \, d\text{phase} (d_1d_2)^q$ which would be required for entropy to be 0. We suggest that for both conditions to hold, one requires that $d_1d_2 = d$ and we suggest that this is not the case because it would mean that the equilibrium process did nothing.

References

1. Du Juilin, Property of Tsallis Entropy and entropy increase (2007 or later)
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/0802.3424>
2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sackur%E2%80%93Tetrode_equation